

The Impact of Concha Bullosa and Deviated Nasal Septum on Chronic Rhinosinusitis: A Retrospective CT-Based Study

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Abstract:

Background: A CT scan distinctly reveals the structural differences of concha bullosa (CB) and deviated nasal septum (DNS) in many cases. These changes may, however, induce mechanical obstruction in the drainage channel, leading to sinusitis.

Objective: Therefore, we performed a retrospective CT-based study to evaluate the influence of CB and DNS on chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS).

Materials and Methods: This retrospective cross-sectional study involved 147 patients at the Department of Otorhinolaryngology in a tertiary care institution in Mumbai. We examined the CT scan reports of individuals with chronic sinusitis to find all variations of CB and DNS.

Results: Among 147 patients, 68 (46.3%) had CB, including 11 (7.4%) with bulbar CB, 5 (3.4%) with widespread CB, and 52 (34.4%) with lamellar CB. 124 patients, or 84.9% of the total cohort, had DNS. Of these, 46% exhibited left-sided DNS, whereas 54% displayed right-sided DNS. In our study, we identified CB in 17 (34%) of the 50 frontal sinusitis cases, 49 (46.23%) of the 106 maxillary sinusitis cases, 27 (43.55%) of the 62 ethmoidal sinusitis cases, and 12 (33.33%) of the 36 sphenoidal sinusitis cases. Every variant of sinusitis exhibited an increased prevalence of right-sided DNS. We observed no statistically significant correlation between CB and DNS, nor between CB and CRS, nor between DNS and CRS, aside from frontal sinusitis.

Conclusion: CRS is a complicated disease with many causes. Differences in anatomy, like concha bullosa and deviated nasal septum DNS, play a big part in how it starts and how long it lasts. This study seeks to elucidate the clinical significance of these discrepancies and their potential impact on patient management by analyzing CT scans in relation to CRS. We advocate the concurrent assessment of the complex etiology and anatomical differences contributing to CRS.

Keywords: Concha bullosa, Deviated Nasal Septum, Chronic sinusitis, CT scan.

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Introduction

Computed tomography (CT) is the preferred tool for detailed assessment of the paranasal sinuses and nasal cavities, revealing various anatomical variations [1,2]. Changes in these areas can impact the drainage of mucus. They include concha bullosa, deviated nasal septum, uncinata process variations, ethmoid bulla, paradoxical middle turbinate, agger nasi, and Haller cells [1].

A concha bullosa is an air-filled cavity within a nasal concha (turbinate) [3]. This condition, which is characterized by the presence of a pneumatized cavity within the turbinate, is a common anatomical variant, occurring in up to 50% of the population. Based on its location, we can classify it into three types: lamellar concha bullosa, bulbous concha

bullosa, and extensive concha bullosa. A disease that affects the paranasal sinuses can impact a concha bullosa, resulting in mucosal thickening, mucus retention, mucocele, and pyocele within the concha bullosa. The concha bullosa can also cause mechanical obstruction, disrupting the drainage pathway and resulting in sinusitis [1].

In some cases, a significantly enlarged concha bullosa can protrude and block the opening of a nearby sinus, potentially resulting in recurrent sinusitis [3]. Most patients with concha bullosa are asymptomatic, with the condition often being discovered during evaluations for headaches. It is also common for these patients to have concurrent nasal septum deviation and sinusitis [4].

The columellar septum is composed of the medial crura of the alar cartilage, while the membranous septum is composed of two layers of skin. Thus, the nasal septum can be divided into two distinct components. Septal deformities include conditions such as dislocation, hypertrophy, deviated nasal septum, and spurring. A localized hematoma or displaced fragments overlapping can cause a DNS to migrate forward, change shape into a C- or S-shape, form spurs, or become thicker [5]. Symptoms of nasal septum deviation include nasal congestion, headaches, anosmia (loss of scent), sinusitis due to blocked sinus openings, and epistaxis (nosebleeds) [5]. The septum mucosa undergoes alterations in histopathology in cases of DNS. This encompasses the basement membrane, lamina propria, and ciliated columnar cell epithelium. Squamous metaplasia and lymphocyte infiltration are more severe on the concave side of the nasal cavity. Furthermore, the convex side contains a greater number of inflammatory cells, fewer serous and mucinous glands, and a prolonged clearance time for saccharin [5]. This could result in sinusitis due to mucosal blockage.

Clinical evaluation and rhinoscopy primarily diagnose Chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS), an inflammation of the paranasal sinuses, which is a prevalent and debilitating condition [1,6]. It is characterized by symptoms such as persistent nasal congestion, drainage from the nose or into the throat, facial pain and pressure, and an altered sense of scent [5].

The specific impact of concha bullosa and DNS on the severity and prevalence of sinusitis remains a topic of ongoing research, despite the established association between anatomical variations and CRS. The correlation between these anatomical variations and CRS has been the subject of numerous studies; however, the results have been inconsistent, with some studies reporting a substantial association and others failing to establish a substantial link.

Researchers have not extensively investigated the interaction between concha bullosa types and DNS location in the context of CRS. In the present investigation, we delve into these interactions.

Therefore, we performed a retrospective CT-based study to evaluate the influence of CB and DNS on CRS.

Material and Methods

The Department of Otorhinolaryngology at Grant Government Medical College and Sir JJ Group of Hospitals, Mumbai, conducted the current cross-sectional investigation from March 2022 to October 2024. The study included patients between the ages of 18 and 60, diagnosed with chronic sinusitis symptoms or nasal obstruction, and those recommended for a CT scan. We excluded from our study patients under the age of 18, those with any congenital deformity or disease of the nasal cavity, paranasal sinuses, or its surrounding structures, odontogenic sinusitis, acute rhinosinusitis, sinus malignancies, or those unwilling to participate in investigations.

We determined a sample size of 147 using the formula $n=4pq/L2$, with a prevalence of 88.5% from Bhandary and Kamath. We attained the sample size through consecutive sampling. The medical records department provided socio-demographic information of the patients. The radiology department provided the CT scan reports.

Statistical Analysis

We inputted the data into a pre-validated case record form and then entered it into Microsoft Excel version 2021 (Microsoft Incorporation). The present study authors employed SPSS version 21 (IBM Incorporation) to conduct the analysis. We conducted descriptive analysis on continuous variables using the mean and standard deviation, and on categorical variables using the median and percentage. We employed the Shapiro-Wilk test to confirm the normality of the data. We employed the Chi-square test to identify an association between various variables. We implemented logistic regression to determine the causal relationship between sinusitis and concha bullosa.

Results

The cross-sectional investigation, which analyzed data from 147 patients, produced the following results.

Table 1: Distribution of Concha Bullosa (CB) in patients (n=147)

Location of CB		Frequency	Percent
Bulbar	Bilateral	6	4
	Left	1	0.68
	Right	4	2.72
Extensive	Bilateral	2	1.36
	Right	3	2.04
Lamellar	Bilateral	20	13.70
	Left	23	15.64
	Right	9	6.12
No CB	Absent	79	53.74
Total		147	100.0

Figure 1: Bar graphs showing the status of Concha Bullosa (CB) and types of sinusitis. The status of Concha Bullosa (CB) and types of sinusitis.

Patient characteristics at the outset: Of the 147 patients with a mean age of 33.39 ± 10.45 years, 53 (36.1%) were female and 94 (63.9%) were male. A total of 68 patients (46.3%) had CB, with 11 patients (7.4%) having bulbar CB, 5 patients (3.4%) having extensive CB, and 52 patients (34.4%) having lamellar CB.

Table 1 presents the information regarding CB. 124 patients, or 84.9% of the total, had DNS. 46% of these had left-sided DNS, while 54% had right-sided DNS. Researchers conducted a study on four distinct varieties of sinusitis. Of the 147 patients, 106 (72.6%) had maxillary sinusitis, 62 (42.5%) had ethmoidal sinusitis, 50 (34.2%) had frontal sinusitis, and 36 (24.7%) had sphenoidal sinusitis. We determined the association between each type of sinusitis, DNS, and CB. We discovered that 17

(34%) of the 50 patients with frontal sinusitis also had CB (Figure 1). The presence of CB was statistically significantly associated with frontal sinusitis (Pearson $\chi^2=4.330$, $df=1$, $p=0.037$, Crammer's $V=0.172$). Out of 106 patients, 49 (46.23%) had maxillary sinusitis, 27 (43.55%) had ethmoidal sinusitis, and 12 (33.33%) had sphenoidal sinusitis (Figure 1). Nevertheless, there was no significant correlation between the presence of CB and other categories of sinusitis (Table 2).

Patients with left lamellar CB ($n=16$) exhibited the most prevalent form of maxillary sinusitis. Patients with bilateral lamellar CB ($n=8$) exhibited the most prevalent form of ethmoidal sinusitis. Patients with left lamellar CB ($n=6$) exhibited the most prevalent form of frontal sinusitis. Patients with left lamellar CB ($n=4$) exhibited the most prevalent form of

sphenoidal sinusitis. 88 (83.02%) of the 106 patients diagnosed with maxillary sinusitis had DNS. Similarly, we identified DNS in 52 (81.25%) patients out of 64 with ethmoidal sinusitis, 43 (86.46%) patients out of 50 with frontal sinusitis, and 32 (88.89%) patients out of 36 with sphenoidal sinusitis (Figure 2).

Nevertheless, the presence of DNS did not have a significant association with any sinusitis (Table 2). Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the specifics of patients who suffer from sinusitis with CB and sinusitis

with DNS. Patients with right-sided DNS (n=52) exhibited the most prevalent form of maxillary sinusitis. Patients with right-sided DNS (n=29) exhibited the most prevalent form of ethmoidal sinusitis.

Patients with right-sided DNS (n=26) exhibited the most prevalent form of frontal sinusitis. Patients with right-sided DNS (n=18) exhibited the most prevalent form of sphenoidal sinusitis. Consequently, the incidence of sinusitis was higher among patients with right-sided DNS.

Table 2: Association of Sinusitis with Concha Bullosa (CB) and Deviated Nasal Septum (DNS).

Sinusitis	Association with CB				Association with DNS			
	Pearson χ^2	df	p-value	Crammer's V	Pearson χ^2	df	p-value	Crammer's V
Maxillary	0.018	1	0.894	0.011	1.106	1	0.293	0.087
Ethmoidal	0.238	1	0.626	0.040	0.095	1	0.758	0.025
Frontal	4.330	1	0.037	0.172	0.068	1	0.795	0.022
Sphenoidal	3.034	1	0.082	0.144	0.585	1	0.444	0.063

In 106 patients with maxillary sinusitis, 45 patients (42.45%) had both CB and DNS. Of the 62 patients diagnosed with ethmoidal sinusitis, 23 (37.1%) exhibited both CB and DNS. 16 (32%) of the 50 patients with frontal sinusitis had both CB and DNS. Of the 36 patients diagnosed with sphenoidal

sinusitis, 11 (30.56%) exhibited both CB and DNS. We determined the association by cross tabulating the presence of CB and DNS. There was no statistically significant correlation between DNS and CB (Pearson $\chi^2=2.170$, $df=1$, $p=0.141$, Crammer's $V=0.122$).

Table 3: Logistic Regression of Sinusitis with Concha Bullosa (CB) and Deviated Nasal Septum (DNS).

Sinusitis	Regression with CB		Regression with DNS	
	Odd's Ratio	p-value	Odd's Ratio	p-value
Maxillary	0.995	0.903	1.907	0.274
Ethmoidal	1.195	0.599	1.135	0.786
Frontal	2.152	0.034	0.777	0.618
Sphenoidal	2.137	0.061	0.566	0.341

We conducted the logistic regression model separately to determine the impact of CB and DNS on the likelihood of sinusitis in the participants.

Table 3 revealed a statistically significant association between the presence of CB and the presence of frontal sinusitis. The model was statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.031 and an $X^2(1)$ value of 4.646. It accurately classified 66% of cases and explained 4.3% (Naglekerke R2)

of the variance in frontal sinusitis presentation. Participants without CB had a 2.152-fold increased likelihood of frontal sinusitis presentation.

However, Table 3 revealed no significant correlation between the remaining sinusitis categories and CB. In the same vein, the logistic regression models did not produce a statistically significant correlation between each type of sinusitis and DNS (Table 3).

Figure 2: Bar graphs showing the status of Deviated Nasal Septum (DNS) and types of sinusitis

Discussion:

Any physiological, anatomical, or pathological alteration in the drainage of the paranasal sinuses causes chronic rhinosinusitis, a condition very commonly diagnosed. Malpani et al. [5] have explained in detail the etiology of this condition. They have stated that several factors contribute to the development of CRS. Among these are asthma, dental infections involving premolars and molars that cause maxillary sinusitis, nasal polyps, and HIV-related illnesses where opportunistic microorganisms like fungi, microsporidia, and Pseudomonas aeruginosa can lead to CRS [5]. Disorders of the mucociliary lining, like cystic fibrosis, primary ciliary dyskinesia, and Kartagener's syndrome, also play a part by making it harder to clear out mucus and swelling in the sinuses [5]. Moreover, the condition is associated with medications such as steroids, chemotherapy drugs, immunosuppressants, and nasal sprays, as well as exposure to harmful environmental pollutants, occupational chemicals, dust, and noxious gases. Microorganisms, including viruses, bacteria like Staphylococcus aureus, and fungi, produce toxins that provoke inflammation in the paranasal sinus mucosa [5]. However, in the

present study, we studied and correlated two very prevalent anatomical variations, concha bullosa and deviated nasal septum, with CRS. This study looks back at the past and finds that concha bullosa and DNS have a big effect on the number of people who get CRS and how bad it is. By analyzing CT scans of patients diagnosed with CRS, we were able to identify the presence of these anatomical variations and assess their correlation with sinusitis severity. Our results highlight the role of concha bullosa and DNS in the pathophysiology of CRS and underscore the importance of considering these anatomical factors in clinical practice. Similar studies [4, 7-13] studied the prevalence and association of CB, DNS, and CRS. However, these studies have not examined the correlation between different types of CB and CRS, nor the relationship between DNS and CRS. The present study analyzed the prevalence of CB, DNS, and CRS and the association of CB with DNS, CB with CRS, and DNS with CRS.

The current retrospective study involved 147 patients, of whom 68 (46.3%) had CB, 11 (7.4%) had bulbar CB, 5 (3.4%) had extensive CB, and 52 (34.4%) had lamellar CB. DNS was present in 124 (84.9%) of the patients. Out of these, 46% had left-

sided DNS while 54% had right-sided DNS. CB and DNS coexisted in 61 (41.5%) of the total patients, whereas it was 87.5% in Bhandary et al. [4] Yigit et al. [14] and Uygur et al. [15] studied the angle of deviation and degree of pneumatization in concha in detail, concluding that the septal deviation angle can increase the pneumatization. Grymer et al. reported DNS as a genetic condition, but Erkan et al. discussed the possibility of CB and DNS influencing each other [16, 17]. The present study found a weak statistically significant association between CB and DNS, similar to studies [4, 10]. Various studies [9, 11, 18] have reported a statistically significant association between CB and contralateral DNS, which contrasts with our findings.

In the current study, we noted the prevalence of CB in 17 (34%) of the total 50 frontal sinusitis patients, 49 (46.23%) of the total 106 maxillary sinusitis patients, 27 (43.55%) of the total 62 ethmoidal sinusitis patients, and 12 (33.33%) of the total 36 sphenoidal sinusitis patients. All types of frontal sinusitis showed a statistically significant association with CB. Kalairasi et al. [21] reported similar findings to our present study. Several studies [7, 8, 19, 20] reported no association. A case study revealed secondary frontal sinusitis and orbital complications in a middle-aged Korean man with a CB mucocele, recommending a detailed evaluation for such patients.

Meanwhile, a middle-aged woman reported secondary maxillary sinusitis [22, 23]. Nadas et al. [24] studied the grades of pneumatization of concha and sinusitis, concluding a doubtful correlation between CRS and CB. The present study found that right-sided DNS was more common in sinusitis patients than left-sided DNS, but did not find any statistically significant association between DNS and CRS, contrary to the findings of Javadrashid et al. [12].

Many studies [13, 25] have found no statistically significant association between DNS, CB, and CRS, but they have also reported some peculiar findings, such as the impact of infundibular size and mean sinus volume on CB and DNS. According to Qualliotine et al. [26], their study is the first to show that CB has a big effect on the quality of life of people with CRS and that surgery may help ease these symptoms.

Despite the inconclusive results from the above literature, a study found that successful surgeries for patients with DNS/CB significantly reduced the number of annual examinations for acute rhinosinusitis, antibiotic prescriptions, and overall healthcare costs. These results suggest that promoting surgical intervention could help lower the frequency and financial burden of ARS in these patients [27]. Various causes, such as anatomical,

physiological, or pathological, can cause CRS, but it's important to consider each cause separately without ruling out the possibility of the other. The present study limited its comparison to only anatomical variations based on CT scan findings; we recommend a detailed study of the other contributing factors as well.

Conclusion

CRS is a condition with many causes, and differences in anatomy like concha bullosa and DNS are very important to how it develops and stays. To find out what these changes mean in terms of clinical significance and possible effects on CRS, this study will look back at CT scan results that were used for patient management. The results of this study have the potential to enhance the existing corpus of knowledge on CRS and inform evidence-based clinical practices, thereby enhancing the outcomes of patients with this chronic and debilitating condition.

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